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ETHICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENTREPRENEURIAL CULTURE

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the social analysis of the ethical foundations of the development of entrepreneurial culture, describing the specific features of entrepreneurial culture, the role of ethics in the development of entrepreneurial activity and the formation of entrepreneurial culture, including their ethical foundations. The social analysis of ethical foundations in the practice of forming and developing entrepreneurial culture, and its popularization in the world economy, is presented. In a market economy, the role of entrepreneurial activity in ensuring the socio-economic well-being of the country, society, and the population is great. According to the results of the social analysis, it is proposed to define the concept of entrepreneurial culture as one of the mandatory courses in the training of sociologists, philosophers, managers, and economists in all higher educational institutions. The purpose of this article is to identify the role of entrepreneurial culture in many areas of business culture and in the modern social technology of material production of social life. The main method of entrepreneurial culture is a general scientific ethical analysis, with the help of which the author considers the culture of the individual in the practice of entrepreneurial activity. Entrepreneurial culture, by its essence, is a mass tool of the system of behavior based on moral, legal, aesthetic, and social values in organizing the economic activity of an entrepreneur, who acquires entrepreneurial culture through entrepreneurial activity. Entrepreneurial culture is studied through social sciences, and its relevance does not cause the slightest doubt among representatives of the social sphere. This is because entrepreneurial culture directly covers interpersonal relationships and communications. In conclusion, the author suggests teaching entrepreneurs' entrepreneurial culture, and in higher education institutions, including the inclusion of personal ethical standards in the curriculum, as a mandatory course and method of educating people in entrepreneurial activity, regulating entrepreneurial culture.

KEYWORDS: Entrepreneur, Entrepreneurial Activity, Entrepreneurial Personality, Entrepreneurial Culture, Ethical Values, Legal Values, Aesthetic Values, Social Values.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the conditions of market relations, entrepreneurship is one of the important factors in the development of all spheres of society. Entrepreneurial activity allows members of society not only to obtain economic benefits but also to solve social problems, create new jobs, and introduce innovations. At the same time, the cultural and ethical aspects of entrepreneurial activity are one of the main criteria for its stability and maintaining public trust. Therefore, in the current digital era, entrepreneurial activity and culture cannot be measured by certain established standards, because this area of activity, along with the demand for social, economic, and political freedom from the individual, occupies a special place in the economic development of the state and ensures the socio-economic well-being of the population.

It is known that entrepreneurial activity has existed since the emergence of human society. It is from this period that an entrepreneurial culture is formed in an entrepreneur. In particular, the views of ancient scholars on entrepreneurial culture are mainly based on the principles of economic development, public administration, and morality. Plato emphasizes the need to limit the economic activity of the state for society to be just. In his opinion, the state offers to control economic activity and eliminate economic inequality in society. As a result, his idea that "the importance of economic freedom in the stable and prosperous existence of a just society rises to a high level" [1. -B. 95-96.] is evidence of the mutual harmony of state and entrepreneurial relations in the stability of society. After all, social well-being in society is directly dependent on the development of entrepreneurial activity. Another ancient Greek philosopher, Aristotle, analyzed the role of property management and trade in social life and developed the first principles of political economy. It is clear from this that Aristotle considers trade to be an important factor in the development of society and sees economic development as one of the main directions of state policy.

We can see the formation and development of an entrepreneurial culture in the culture, values, customs, and traditions of the peoples of Central Asia. In particular, this issue is also addressed in the ancient manuscript "Avesta". Starting from the "Avesta", philosophical and moral thoughts glorifying human labor, condemning dependence, and ideas teaching hard work, special attention is paid to the well-being of society and human life [2. - P. 248], and this is a hint that people should rely on

entrepreneurship. As we know, the "Avesta" is not only a religious source, but also a source telling about the history of peoples, and it also contains information about the farming and animal husbandry of the Turanian peoples. In particular, there are a number of ideas about the structural structure of society. "In ancient farming regions, initially, the top of the management system was the priests.

They are "owners of cattle and pastures". Warrior soldiers are Aryans, considered property owners after the priests" [3. - P. 25-26. This means that property relations have been systematically regulated in the territories of our country since ancient times. At the same time, international trade routes also played an important role in the development of entrepreneurial activity in the territories of our homeland. In particular, the Great Silk Road served as a bridge connecting the civilizations of the East and the West, which directly played an important role in the development of entrepreneurial activity.

The Great Silk Road is the first intercontinental caravan route (2nd century BC - 15th century AD) that connected the countries of the East and the West for the first time in ancient times and in the Middle Ages. The priceless products transported along the Great Silk Road are directly related to Chinese silk. This shows that Western societies were unaware of the secrets of sericulture for a long time. The scientific and practical study of the historical, socio-economic, and cultural aspects of the Great Silk Road began with scientists from many countries in the second half of the 19th century, and scientists from Western Europe, Russia, and Japan made a significant contribution to its research. In particular, the "Encyclopedia of the Great Silk Road" was published in Japan. In 1877, the famous German scientist Karl Richthofen, in his major scientific work "China", called the system of roads connecting various regions of the vast European and Asian countries the "Silk Road"; later, the term "Great Silk Road" was adopted. It is clear from this that the cultural ties of peoples improved through the "Great Silk Road", and through this, norms were formed in entrepreneurial culture.

We can also see that the rules of our ancestors for conducting business activities are perfectly described in our national Islamic religion. In many verses of the Holy Quran, the basis of the Islamic religion, we can see views on property, property relations, entrepreneurship, trade, and various other economic relations. In particular, the Holy Quran encourages people to work honestly, be thrifty, be kind and

compassionate, and be honest. It also calls on people to make the most of all material blessings and resources (land). The Holy Quran also pays special attention to any economic property. The concept of property in Islam, its essence, is the recognition that wealth in the hands of people is the wealth of Allah, and people are only His stewards on earth [4. – B. 5.]. It is clear from this that the state, religion, education, upbringing, family, neighborhood, governance, values, culture, law, and other social factors influenced the formation of the initial manifestations of entrepreneurial activity in the regions of our country. In turn, these institutions play an important role in the development of entrepreneurial culture.

In addition, scholars who lived during the Central Asian Renaissance also made a significant contribution to the development of entrepreneurial culture. One of them was Abu Nasr Al-Farabi, who in his work “The City of Virtuous People” said: “Voluntary free actions that lead to happiness are beautiful actions” [5. –P. 231], emphasizing that this idea is a guarantee of entrepreneurial relations in social processes in society. In the current conditions, the concept of entrepreneurial culture is defined differently by scholars. We can give many examples of this. Entrepreneurial culture is a set of clear, established principles and methods of entrepreneurial activity by subjects in accordance with the legal norms (laws, regulations), business customs, ethical rules, and standards of civilized business conduct in society [6]. Entrepreneurial culture regulates the activities of an individual and controls their compliance with the general rules of society. While this means that he can conduct his activities freely, it does not mean that he is free from not following the established rules and methods in his activities.

The user establishes certain barriers to restrict the manifestation of economic freedoms in all respects in order to protect the interests and economic freedoms of other participants in entrepreneurial activity and other subjects of the market economy in general, society. This means that the interests of society prevail over everything. Based on the above, we can define entrepreneurial culture as follows. Entrepreneurial culture is an activity that is formed and develops within the framework of a structure of legal, moral, economic, and social relations based on cooperation between the individual, society, and the state [7. – B.75].

Private property is considered valuable, inviolable, and equal to all other forms of ownership, and the entrepreneur acts as a promoter of business and creative activity. His profession requires serious

work, earning money. This determines his prestige. An entrepreneur understands the importance of his work. For this reason, he demands a responsible approach to work from his partners and is one of the first to support him. Private entrepreneurial activity leads to the development of productive forces and imposes specific obligations on the entrepreneur. The elements of entrepreneurial culture are, firstly, the general element of entrepreneurial culture is its legality, secondly, strict fulfillment of obligations arising from legal documents, contractual relations, and legal transactions, commercial turnover, which are manifested in the infliction of material and non-material damage to partners, competitors, consumers, and employees, and thirdly, honest conduct of business entities. Honesty towards people, consumers, partners, and the state is a leading sign of entrepreneurial culture.

It is important for entrepreneurs to adhere to general ethical standards, including professional ethics, generally accepted rules for doing business, the level of their requirements, adherence to customs existing in society, the level of knowledge necessary to conduct a legitimate business, etc. The manifestation of legal and ethical criteria in entrepreneurial culture includes the following relationships: with the state, society, consumers, employees, partners, competitors, and other business entities, together with current laws, standards, rules, norms, and relationships that directly or indirectly affect the development of entrepreneurship.

Entrepreneurship is a type of activity aimed at making a profit systematically, not by various methods, but only on legal grounds. In the formation of entrepreneurial culture, the first place is taken by the civilized external business environment, social and state thinking, and legal norms that determine the rights and obligations of entrepreneurs, protecting them from an aggressive environment. In addition, the institutional aspect of entrepreneurial culture corresponds to the concept of the “external environment of entrepreneurial culture”. We understand “institutionalism” as the historical form of organizing the joint activities of individuals and their basic principles that have some degree of influence on the process, whether it is subjective or objective.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The system of studying the literature on the topic of sociological and ethical analysis of the ethical foundations of the development of entrepreneurial culture is based on the general scientific methods of applied sociology and the ethical foundations of the

development of entrepreneurial culture. To achieve the goals and objectives of this article, materials obtained as a result of scientific research by sociologists, philosophers, and economists were used. On this basis, a sociological survey was conducted among entrepreneurs operating in the Namangan region of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The survey results showed that the adherence to ethical standards by entrepreneurs operating in our region is of great importance in the formation of an entrepreneurial culture in their activities. It should also be noted that there is a significant difference between the cultures of entrepreneurs of Eastern and Western countries. In the formation of the ethical foundations of entrepreneurial culture, ethical standards, professional culture, social responsibility, and innovative thinking of members of society play an important role.

These elements of culture are inextricably linked with the personal values of the entrepreneur, and the process of their formation occurs under the influence of education, social environment, and national mentality. This requires an approach to the topic based on national mentality and values.

3. RESULTS AND SCIENTIFIC INNOVATION

The results of the study of the ethical foundations of the development of entrepreneurial culture showed that the ethical foundations of the entrepreneurial culture of entrepreneurs operating in Uzbekistan are reflected in the national mentality, values, and traditions of our people. Because it means that the moral standards, professional culture, social responsibility, and innovative thinking of the Uzbek people have been formed for a long time, we can also see this from the social views of thinkers who lived in our homeland on professional culture. For example, al-Hashim as Samarkandiy emphasizes that "It is a requirement of religion for a person to have a profession. Therefore, it is necessary for a person to live by labor" [8. - P. 49]. It is clear from this that the mention of verses in the Holy Quran, the sacred source of Islam, calling on people to work, earn their livelihood in an honest way, and help others through their labor, is an indication that Islam calls on a person who believes in entrepreneurship.

We can also see that Abu Nasr Farabi, in his views, specifically touched upon the moral foundations of entrepreneurial culture. For example, in his work "The City of Virtuous People," he wrote: "Acquiring property that does not harm people and generations is a useful thing; in this, education that makes the soul and body worthy of respect with the help of laws

is important. Accumulating wealth and possessing property that harms only others is a bad habit" [5. - P. 38]. In his views, Farabi studied the national mentality of people in connection with religious moral norms. Because entrepreneurial culture and religious moral norms are inextricably linked, one complements the other. It is clear from this that the moral views of Islam play an important role in the views of scholars who lived and worked in the regions of our country on entrepreneurial culture.

Because, in Islam, special attention is paid to moral standards, choice of profession, and social responsibility. In particular, special attention is paid to the entrepreneur's kindness to his employees and customers. We can also see this in the 10th verse of Surah Fatir of the "Quran". "... (Every) good word ascends to Him. And the righteous deed, (Allah raises to His court)" [9. - P. 39]. This means that the culture of communication is of particular importance in the development of entrepreneurial culture. The reason is that the culture of communication is one of the important moral standards of a person and is one of the factors determining the spiritual image of an entrepreneur. At the same time, the spirituality of an entrepreneur is related to the social responsibility of an entrepreneur. In general, by developing an entrepreneurial culture, an entrepreneur creates favorable conditions for social relations, improves the favorable environment for relations, and helps to find contours for entering into social relations. Thus, entrepreneurial activity plays an important role in solving not only economic, but also socially complex problems in society, and opens up new opportunities for preventing socio-economic problems. Income earned through entrepreneurial activity helps to solve problems of socio-economic development. In interdisciplinary analysis, the main feature of the entrepreneurial culture is that it ensures the transformation of the socio-economic development of the country.

4. DISCUSSION

Although there are not as many "world-famous scientists" in the field of entrepreneurial culture as in other fields of science, their opinions form the basis of this field. Entrepreneurial culture is considered not just a set of individual cultures, but a complex philosophical and social phenomenon that affects the sustainable development and profitability of entrepreneurial activity. The views of scientists on entrepreneurial culture are important in terms of its basic principles, such as ethical standards, professional culture, social responsibility, and innovative thinking, as well as the impact of ethical

norms on scientific activity and socio-economic relations in society. Therefore, prominent scientists from developed countries emphasize the need to adhere to an entrepreneurial culture to maintain social progress. Many scientists have studied the views on the culture of an entrepreneurial person as a scientific study, and we can divide them into areas of activity (production, commercial, financial, intermediary, etc.), areas of development (small, medium, large), areas of the nature of activity (constructive, destructive, legal, criminal) and areas of value aspects (moral, aesthetic, entrepreneurial). In particular, representatives of philosophy, sociology, and other social sciences are more interested in the area of value aspects.

In the culture of entrepreneurship, it is important to adhere to ethics and moral standards. By following this principle, an entrepreneur adheres to the principles of honesty, responsibility, fairness, and respect in relations with employees, partners, customers, and society. These principles of entrepreneurial culture form a collective culture, strengthen mutual trust between the entrepreneur and the employee, employee and employee, entrepreneur and consumer, and, together with increasing employee participation in entrepreneurial activities, reduce staff dissatisfaction. In turn, this contributes to the long-term success of entrepreneurial activities. Trust in entrepreneurial culture is a key success factor, affecting both internal processes (teamwork, motivation, innovation) and external relations (with customers and partners). It increases efficiency, speeds up decision-making, reduces employee turnover, and develops loyalty. A culture of trust is based on transparency, reliability, mutual respect, and the consideration of the interests of all parties.

Compliance with ethical standards in entrepreneurial culture is especially important in the context of reforms in Uzbekistan. In particular, the development of an entrepreneurial culture in an individual has a positive impact on all areas of social development. We can cite as an example the fact that the organization and development of new entrepreneurial activities in our country has risen to the level of state policy. As evidence of this, we can see that August 20 has been declared "Entrepreneurs' Day" in our country since 2021, in the open dialogue held by the President of our country, Sh. Mirziyoyev, with entrepreneurs, on August 20, 2025, we can see that our state places great trust in entrepreneurs. Sh. Mirziyoyev also highly appreciated this meeting and expressed the following opinion: "It would be correct to say that it is a lively and sincere dialogue space

that serves to strengthen mutual trust between the state and business" [10]. Indeed, the state places great trust in them to organize and develop entrepreneurial activity in our country. As a result of the trust shown by the state, entrepreneurial activity is developing in every sector of our society. At the meeting, Sh. Mirziyoyev specifically touched upon this issue and said: "Every sector, every region, every neighborhood - only when entrepreneurs act, listen to them, and are given trust will develop and prosper" [10].

Also, professional culture has a special place in the development of entrepreneurial culture. Because professional culture is the basis of entrepreneurial culture, it forms its spiritual and personal elements: knowledge, skills, thinking, moral standards, and values. It determines how an entrepreneur and their team act, make decisions, and interact with the external environment, which directly affects the success, legitimacy, and efficiency of entrepreneurship. In general, the professional culture of an entrepreneur is a combination of specific theoretical knowledge and practical skills in their type of activity. One of the indicators of having a professional culture is the level of qualification. In addition, the development of entrepreneurial culture involves the transfer of the professional culture of an entrepreneur to a culture that values innovation and risk-taking, as well as the development of a sense of social responsibility among employees.

The main strategy of the professional culture of an entrepreneur is to encourage open communication with employees and customers, create conditions for the creation of new ideas, that is, to give employees the freedom and independence to implement their ideas. Encouraging innovation, recognizing successes and challenges, and demonstrating transparency from top to bottom are also very important for success. Thus, professional culture is a means of personal and social development of entrepreneurial activity, a guarantee of the progress of society. Social responsibility in entrepreneurial activity can be defined as a social action that benefits society. The activity of an entrepreneur should not only benefit themselves, but also contribute to the well-being of society. Any decision of an entrepreneur related to their activity should take into account social, ethical, and environmental aspects.

If an entrepreneur harms society or the environment in any way, he are considered socially irresponsible. Some ways to demonstrate social responsibility include implementing sustainable business practices to reduce carbon emissions, supporting social initiatives, providing jobs to local

people, and treating employees well. Entrepreneurs should have a positive impact on society. In short, through the innovative thinking of an entrepreneur, he can solve a wide range of social problems facing society and himself. This is because entrepreneurial activity should not only generate profit but also contribute to the well-being of society, so the social responsibility of entrepreneurship is crucial for creating a sustainable and inclusive society. By integrating social responsibility into their business models, they can have a positive impact on society,

build strong brands, and stimulate economic growth. International cooperation can foster peace between countries by working not only for the benefit of their employees and customers, but also by helping less developed countries to outsource their labor.

Therefore, to create a strong and united world, entrepreneurs must be socially and economically responsible.

In general, the indicators of the professional culture of an entrepreneurial person are as follows.

Table 1

No.	Professional culture indicators	Content
1	Knowledge and skills	Entrepreneur's own field according to enough knowledge and practical to skill has to be
2	Responsibility	Own to work, to customers and to partners relatively responsibility with approach
3	Dealing culture	Employees, customers and partners with polite and respect with communication to do
4	Honesty and reliability	In action fair to be and to their promises action to do
5	From time productive use	Work process plan based on organization time to arrive effective to manage
6	Initiative	New idea and projects previously chapter to receive
7	Innovative thinking	Modern technologies and from the news to use aspiration
8	External appearance culture	Entrepreneurship ethics and dress to culture compliance to do
9	In the team work ability	Employees with in cooperation effective activity take progress
10	Himself develop	Permanent accordingly knowledge and experience increasing progress

In order to study important indicators of the professional culture of entrepreneurs operating in our country, a sociological survey was conducted in

the regions of the Fergana Valley (Namangan, Andijan, and Fergana), and the following results were obtained.

Diagram 1

According to the survey results, the majority of respondents identified business culture and responsibility as the most important factors in entrepreneurial activity. This shows that effective communication with customers and a serious approach to work are key factors in entrepreneurial success.

Also, honesty and knowledge the level is also high

was evaluated. Innovative thinking and initiative indicators relatively lower although modern entrepreneurship in development they important importance profession to be able emphasized.

Entrepreneur person's professional culture entrepreneurship of activity efficiency increasing main from factors is one. Because, professionally culture:

- customers trust strengthens ;

- in the team healthy environment creates;
- competitiveness increases ;
- entrepreneurship to develop service does.

5. CONCLUSION

In modern society, entrepreneurship is emerging as the main driving force of the economy. The culture of entrepreneurship not only regulates economic processes but also strengthens the spiritual foundations of social life. Therefore, the role of moral values, responsibility, honesty, and social justice in the development of entrepreneurial culture is of particular importance. The moral foundations of the development of entrepreneurial culture have already been formed by the system of sciences, and theoretical and practical research is being conducted by sociology, cultural studies, ethics, aesthetics, and other disciplines. The sociology of entrepreneurship as a separate discipline by sociologists has formed the direction of the moral foundations of the social study of entrepreneurial culture.

In the context of the information society, the sociology of entrepreneurship has an interdisciplinary nature and is studied through the collective efforts of social and human sciences. The history of the formation of entrepreneurial culture goes back to ancient times, reflecting the wisdom of the people as a special form of human communication, the basis for the development of social relations and connections. The moral foundations of the development of culture in our country and its evolution were formed on the basis of Islamic religious values. In particular, our ancestors,

having thoroughly mastered the teachings of Islam and strictly adhering to its moral norms, successfully engaged in trade, crafts, agriculture, and other areas of entrepreneurship. The increasing importance of Islamic values in the conduct of economic activities with justice, honesty, and social responsibility by citizens engaged in entrepreneurial activities in our country is a positive phenomenon. This, in turn, serves as the basis for engaging in social relations based on mutual trust among citizens engaged in entrepreneurial activities. The priority of the individual factor through the change of the principle of "State - Society - Man" to the principle of "Man - Society - State" means that not only the state and society are responsible for all areas and current issues, but also the person is not without responsibility. That is, the image of the spiritual environment and social space in entrepreneurial activity is largely determined by the personal qualities and qualities of entrepreneurs and owners, their life position, attitude to work and profession, conscience, and sense of responsibility. The results of the study show that entrepreneurial culture cannot develop sustainably without relying on ethical principles. Values such as honesty, responsibility, justice, transparency, and environmental awareness lead an entrepreneur not only to economic success but also to long-term social trust. The formation of entrepreneurial culture in Uzbekistan is closely related to national values, state policy, and the education system. Existing opportunities can be further strengthened by improving ethical foundations.

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REFERENCES

- <https://works.doklad.ru/view/OYUp81gkbLw/all.html>
- O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyevning tadbirkorlar bilan ochiq muloqot shaklida o'tkazilgan uchrashuvdagi nutqi. <https://president.uz/oz/lists/view/8397>
- Qozoqov S. "O'zbekistondagi islohotlar sharoitida tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishning ijtimoiy omillari" [Social factors of entrepreneurship development in the context of reforms in Uzbekistan]. Sotsiologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) dissertatsiyasi. Toshkent-2023. 125 b.
- Qozoqov S. Factors Influencing The Formation of Entrepreneurial Culture. *Academia Globe: Inderscience Research* Vol: 6, No 3, 2026, Page: 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.47134/academia.v6i3.36> <https://academia.pubmedia.id/index.php/Academia/article/view/36>
- Qozoqov S. Tadbirkorlik madaniyati tadbirkorlik tizimini rivojlantirish omili sifatida [Entrepreneurship culture entrepreneurship system develop factor as]. "Sharq tarixi, siyosati va huquqi jurnali" *Oriental Journal*

- of History, Politics and Law, tom 5 № 10 (2025):1-6 betlar.
<https://www.supportscience.uz/index.php/ojhpl>
- Абдуллаев А. ва бошқалар. Кичик бизнес ва хусусий тадбиркорлик: ташкил этиш, режалаштириш, бошқариш [Small business and private entrepreneurship: organization, planning, management]. Тошкент: Фан ва технология. 2005. 444 б.
- Абу Наср Форобий. Фозил одамлар шаҳри [The City of Virtuous People]. – Тошкент: Янги аср авлоди, 2016. 452 б.
- Авесто [Avesta]. А.Маҳкамов таржимаси. –Тошкент: Шарқ, 2001. 248 б.
- Асқаров А. Ўзбек халқининг этногенези ва этник тарихи [Ethnogenesis and ethnic history of the Uzbek people]. Тошкент: Университет. 2007. 339 б.
- Афлотун. Қонунлар [Laws]. Рус тилидан Ўрфон Отажон таржимаси. Тошкент: “Янги аср авлоди”, 2002. 167 б.
- Аҳадқули Холмухаммад ўғли. Савдогарлар устози ёхуд ҳақиқий омад калити [Traders mentor or the key to real luck]. Самарқанд.: Имом Бухорий халқаро маркази нашрети. 2018. – 106 б.
- Ислонда тадбиркорлик ва тижорат одоблари [Entrepreneurship and Commercial Ethics in Islam]. Тошкент.: Ғ. Ғулом номидаги нашриёт-матбаа ижодий уйи. 2016. 76-бет.